

THE CONSTITUTION OF CHAKSINE. PART I

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On the basis of I. R. spectra of chaksine and its derivative, a structure for chaksine has been suggested. It appears that chaksine contains a bicyclic ring with a common N atom.

Siddiqui and Ahmed (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 421) assigned the formula $C_{12}H_{21}O_2N_3$ for the alkaloid of *Cassia absus* isolated by them. But Ray *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 281) suggested that the quaternary base should be formulated as $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_3OH$ and adduced evidence in support of this view. The subsequent work of Siddiqui *et al.* (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1946, 4, 101; vide also *Res. Bull. E. Panjab Univ.*, No. 21, p. 95) tacitly accepted the formula of Ray *et al.*

The present investigation deals with the determination of structure of chaksine. Chaksine has a quaternary nitrogen, the two other nitrogen atoms are non-basic or at the most one is very feebly basic. Siddiqui *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) found that in alcoholic solution a disulphate of chaksine could be isolated, which was extremely susceptible to hydrolysis. This observation has been confirmed by us. Although sodium hydroxide solution liberates ammonia from chaksine very slowly even at 100° ; baryta solution is more effective, and ammonia is copiously evolved on heating. The barium salts of acids obtained by baryta hydrolysis, when distilled with baryta, furnish a liquid showing a very strong pyrrole reaction. The oxidation with permanganate produces oxalic acid, an amino-acid (isolated as copper salt) and a lactone-like compound. Benzoylation of chaksine affords a dibenzoyl benzoate derivative but acetylation causes a breakdown of the molecule, a tri-acetyl derivative $C_9H_{11}O_2N_2.(CO.CH_3)_3$ being formed.

I.R. spectra of chaksine (Fig. 1) reveal the presence of C:N (6.35μ) in the ring. Therefore, in chaksine

is postulated. The broad absorption in the region 3.0μ is due to bonded NH. This NH is part of an ureido group (absorption at 5.8μ and 5.95μ). On heating chaksine sulphate with dilute hydrochloric acid, CO_2 is slowly liberated. This also suggests a grouping NH-CO-NH. The absorption at 7.85μ suggests the

grouping $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{N}-\text{C}=\diagdown \\ \diagdown \end{array}$

FIG. 1
(Chalcino sulphate).

FIG. 2
(Acid sulphate).

FIG. 3
(Acid)

FIG. 4
(Base)

Therefore the structure can be extended to

The NH* is not free but is attached to C, as one molecule of nitrous acid when reacting with chaksine chloride affords chaksine nitrite (cf. Kapur, Gaiind, Narang and Ray, *loc. cit.*, who erroneously described it as $C_9H_{17}O_4N_3$). But when chaksine chloride is allowed to react with a large excess of nitrous acid at $0^\circ-5^\circ$, a basic substance, $C_9H_{16}O_5N_2$ and a nitrite, $C_9H_{15}O_4N_3$, are formed. These products are formed by the interaction of nitrous acid on NH-CO-NH (*vide supra*). Moreover, the I. R. band being broad in the region of 3.0μ suggests that NH is associated instead of being a free NH_2 .

Roth-Kuhn oxidation indicates one C.(CH₃). The positive pyrrole test and the resistance of the molecule to the Hoffmann or Emde degradation indicate a bicyclic structure of which the quaternary N is common to both rings. The I. R. absorption at 7.22μ supports the presence of C-CH₃.

In various degradations, a C₈ residue was generally obtained. Therefore, it is presumed that 8C atoms including (C.CH₃) form the framework of the bicyclic structure. Hence, the formula can be extended to

In the above the residue C₂H₅O has to be accommodated. This probably occurs as CH₂.CH₂.OH, as a tribenzoyl derivative of chaksine can be obtained indicating an alcoholic group. In many reactions 2 C atoms are extruded and bromoform is formed by hypobromite oxidation. Therefore, chaksine is tentatively proposed as

The double bond between 1 and 3 may be in equilibrium with its tautomer between (1) and (2).

Chaksine chloride shows curariform activity (De *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12B**, 358). This activity diminishes and falls with time. The I.R. spectra of chaksine chloride show a band indicating C-Cl. This means the transition of Cl from N to C through the double bond making the molecule lose its quaternary character, and hence, also loss of curariform activity. By the action of fuming nitric acid on chaksine sulphate, several substances, $C_9H_{14}O_5N_3$, $C_6H_{10}O_3N_3$, $C_9H_{15}N_3O_3$, $C_9H_{15}O_3N_3$ and $C_9H_{17}N_3O_2$ have been isolated. These together with their structures, based on the formula proposed, have been described in the Experimental.

Chaksine nitrate with sulphuric acid furnishes several products, one of which is nitrochaksine sulphate (analogy with urea nitrate $\rightarrow$ nitro-urea). There are other products, e.g. $C_{11}H_{16}O_5N_4$, $C_8H_{13}O_3N_3$. The latter has been oxidised to an acid, $C_6H_{10}O_4N_2$. Oxidation with chromic acid affords $(C_9H_{11}O_4N_3)SO_3$, but this substance probably is a mixture although it is crystalline and looks homogeneous under the microscope.

The U.V. spectrum reveals no distinctive features except that the inflection at 271m μ may be due to some kind of conjugation. This may arise from

a possible tautomeric form of the structure proposed. The I.R. spectra of chaksine sulphate in nujol "mull" suggest the presence of the following :

Bands observed in chaksine sulphate.	Probable functional groups and structure assigned.	Bands observed in chaksine sulphate.	Probable functional groups and structure assigned.
3.2 μ broad 3.4 μ	Bonded NH Mull CH	7.62 μ } 7.85 μ }	$\left. \begin{array}{l} \diagup \\ \diagdown \end{array} \right\} C-NH-C$ (unsat. or aromatic)
5.8 μ 5.95 μ } 6.10 μ }	C:O conjugated ester -CO-NH-	8.0 μ } week 8.2 μ }	May be due to strained β -lactam.
6.35 μ	C:N (ring)	8.3 μ } week 8.45 μ }	-CH-NH-CH and -CONH ₂
6.80 μ 7.22 μ	Mull C-H Mull C-H and C-CH ₃	8.80 μ } 9.35 μ }	SO ₄ ²⁻

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Chaksine.—In the present investigation seeds (about 500 lbs.) were extracted essentially by the method of Siddiqui *et al.* (*loc. cit.*, 1935) the yield of the iodide varied from 0.7% to 0.8%. The seeds from Bombay State give lesser yield than the seeds from North India. From the mother-liquors, no isochaksine could be isolated. The pasty mass obtained by the method of Siddiqui *et al.* invariably gave chaksine oxalate with oxalic acid, yield 0.04%.

Hydrolysis with Baryta.—Chaksine sulphate (5.0 g.), suspended in water (100 c.c.), was treated with crystalline barium hydroxide (30 g. in water, 100 c.c.). The mixture

was stirred thoroughly at 60°. After filtration of separated barium sulphate, the solution was heated till the evolution of ammonia had ceased. The concentrated viscous solution was mixed with excess of baryta and dried *in vacuo*. The solids were only distilled affording an oily substance accompanied by much fumes. The ethereal solution of the distillate gave a strong pine shaving reaction, but quickly polymerised when evaporated. Hydrogen chloride converted the ethereal solution of the oil into an amorphous reddish substance, reminiscent of pyrrole red. No crystalline derivative could be prepared of the oil.

Hydrolysis with dilute Hydrochloric Acid.—Chaksine sulphate (1.0 g.) was refluxed with HCl (5%, 25 c. c.) for 3 hours. CO₂ was evolved. The neutralised solution afforded a minute amount of an oxalate, m.p. 132°, recrystallisable from hot water, but in quantities insufficient for characterisation.

Treatment of Chaksine Nitrate with concentrated Sulphuric Acid.—To sulphuric acid (5 c. c. d 1.84) was added chaksine nitrate (2.5 g.) at 0° in small portions with stirring during ½ hour. The stirring was continued for 45 minutes, when a clear solution resulted. The mixture was poured into ice-cold water (150 c. c.). A white solid (I) (1.2 g.) separated and it was collected. The filtrate and washings were neutralised with sodium carbonate when a flocculent precipitate separated. Excess of sodium carbonate was avoided as a part of the precipitate redissolved in excess of the alkali. Filtration was avoided and the weak base was extracted with chloroform. The residue from chloroform was extracted with *N*-HCl. Reprecipitated from the acid extract with sodium carbonate, the base was collected (II, 0.8 g.).

Compound (I) was dissolved in a solution of sodium carbonate (6 g. in 40 c.c. water) by heating for ½ hour at 50°-70°. After standing for 3 hours, the filtered solution was reprecipitated with HCl avoiding excess of (II). The substance (I) was crystallised several times from hot dilute alcohol, m.p. 174° (decomp.). [Found: C, 39.3; H, 6.0; N, 17.0; S, 4.8. (C₁₁H₁₇O₃N₄)₂SO₄ requires C, 39.6; H, 5.2; N, 16.8; S, 4.8 per cent]. The Infra-red spectrum was studied in the form of "mull" in Nujol (Fig. 2). The broad absorption in the region 3.0μ can be due to strongly bonded H of NH or OH but it looks like more of a OH of a COOH group. Absorption at 3.4μ is that of mull. Absorption at 5.8μ and 6.1μ suggests the presence of a CO-NH group. Absorption at 6.5μ is due to a NO₂ group. Absorption at 7.23μ is due to C-H₃. The substance, (I) should be represented as follows on the basis of the structure proposed for chaksine.

The substance (III) was purified by slow crystallisation from acetone. It decomposes in contact with hot solvents. It can be easily dissolved in sodium carbonate and reprecipitated without decomposition, m.p. 160° (decomp.) after crystallisation from acetone. (Found: C, 46.1; H, 6.3; N, 19.6; M. W. from Ba salt, 296. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{16}O_5N_4$: C, 46.5; H, 5.6; N, 19.7 per cent. M.W., 284). The I.R. spectra (Fig. 3) is practically the same as that of substance (I), except that the SO_4^{2-} band is absent and there is a band at 4.6μ . The latter is due to $C\equiv N$. Therefore, (III) is

(III)

The base (II) was purified *via* its oxalate (m.p. 205° decomp., crystallised from dilute alcohol) and picrate, m.p. $185-88^{\circ}$ (decomp.). The base had m.p. 170° (decomp.). (Found: C, 48.7, 48.4; H, 6.0, 6.1; N, 20.7. $C_6H_{12}O_3N_3$ requires C, 48.3; H, 6.5; N, 21.1 per cent). The I.R. spectra (Fig. 4) show the following:

Bands.	Functional groups.	Bands.	Functional groups.
2.9 μ	Bonded NH	5.6 μ	NO_2
5.8	CO-NH	7.25	C-CH ₂
5.95		7.8	Unidentified
6.3	Conjugated double bond		

The substance then probably is

Oxidation of (II) by MnO_2 .—The compound (II, 0.8 g.) was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) containing H_2SO_4 (1.5 c.c.) and was oxidised by MnO_2 (2 g.) added in small portions during 1 hour, the solution being kept on gentle boil. On standing, a sticky substance separated which was removed by filtration. The filtrate on standing a few days deposited a crystalline substance which was crystallised from dilute alcohol containing a few drops of acetic acid. It is an acid and melts at $190-92^{\circ}$ (decomp.). The substance (IV) is difficult to dry as it decomposes slightly. (Found: C, 40.2; H 6.3; N, 17.5. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}O_4N_2$: C, 41.3; H, 5.7; N, 16.1 per cent). The substance on the basis of formula for chaksine is represented by structure (IV).

CONSTITUTION OF CHAKSINE

Action of Nitrous Acid on Chaksine.—The interaction of 1 mole of HNO_2 on 1 mole of chloride afforded a substance, m.p. 221° , which Ray *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) erroneously formulated as $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$. This substance has now been found to be chaksine nitrite and not nitrate, as suggested by Gupta and Mahajan (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 602). The formation of a nitrate by interaction with nitrous acid would be most remarkable.

Chaksine sulphate (5.48 g.) was converted into the chloride by interaction with a solution of $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and cooled to 0° . A solution of sodium nitrite (9.0 g.) in water (100 c.c.), cooled to 0° , was mixed with a solution of HCl (d 1.16, 19 c.c.) in water (100 c.c.), also cooled to 0° . To this was added the cooled chaksine chloride solution during $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours at 0° . The mixture was left at 25° – 30° for 3 hours. After that, the solution was made ammoniacal when a precipitate appeared. This was dissolved in ethyl acetate, dried and from the solution the substance was recovered. The residue gave a highly crystalline oxalate in alcohol, m.p. 298° (decomp.) after several recrystallisations from alcohol (V). The ammoniacal aqueous solution was just acidified with acetic acid, when silky needles separated. These were collected and crystallised successively from hot water, and a mixture of alcohol and ether (VI). The aqueous filtrate on slow evaporation provided a further crop of this substance. It had m.p. 210° (decomp.). It is a quaternary salt; after treatment with alkali in the aqueous alkaline solution strong positive test for a nitrite is obtained. [Found in (V): C, 48.5; H, 6.6; N, 11.8. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4$ requires C, 49.0; H, 6.9; N, 11.4 per cent]. Therefore (V) is the oxalate of the base $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$. [Found in (VI): C, 44.1; H, 6.9; N, 19.5]. The substances are oxalate of

Action of Fuming Nitric Acid on Chaksine Sulphate.—Chaksine sulphate (7.0 g.) was added to fuming nitric acid (95%, 28 c.c.) at 30° in small quantities

A-3.—This substance dissolves in dilute sodium hydroxide solution from which it is reprecipitated by acids. It was purified by conversion into the picrate, which was purified by recrystallisation from acetone-alcohol mixture, m.p. 199° (decomp.). [Found: C, 41.1; H, 4.4; N, 19.2. $C_{15}H_{15}O_{10}N_8$ (*i.e.* picrate of $C_8H_{15}O_2N_3$) requires C, 40.7; H, 4.1; N, 19.0 per cent]. The substance contains $CO-NH_2$ group as it liberates NH_3 on heating with alkali. It has the structure

The filtrate B was made slightly alkaline with NaHCO_3 when a flocculent precipitate separated. This precipitate was treated as follows.

B-1, formed in small yield, readily afforded a picrate (deep yellow needles), m.p. 202° (decomp.) after crystallisation from absolute alcohol. (Found: C, 40.8; H, 4.2; N, 19.6. $C_{17}H_{21}O_{11}N_7$ requires C, 40.9; H, 4.2; N, 19.6 per cent). It is the picrate of chaksine of which the CH_2OH has formed a nitric ester, *i.e.* $\text{CH}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{NO}_2$. The substance responds to the test for a nitrate.

B-2 is sparingly soluble in ether and separates out during the distillation of the ethereal solution. It was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol in beautiful needles, m.p. 174-78° (decomp.). (Found: C, 48.7; H, 6.7; N, 20.6. $C_{11}H_{15}O_8N_4$ requires C, 48.9; H, 6.7; N, 20.7 per cent). M.W. (cryoscopic in acetic acid), 266. This substance is the nitric ester at CH_2OH and the pentavalent N is in the aminic oxide form, *i.e.* $:\text{N}=\text{O}$ form.

The substance B-3 was not obtained in an analytically pure condition.

B-4 was initially purified by fractional precipitation of its alcoholic solution with petroleum ether. Finally, it was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and petroleum ether

when it had m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 41.0; H, 6.9; N, 18.2. Calc for C₈H₁₁O₃N₃: C, 41.1; H, 6.4; N, 18.0 per cent). It is represented as shown below.

In another experiment the ratio of chaksine sulphate to fuming nitric acid was altered to 2 g. of chaksine to 5 c.c. of fuming nitric acid at 20°. The products were isolated as per scheme below. The products C-1, C-2 and C-4 were formed in fairly good yields.

C-1 is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate, sodium carbonate and ammonia. It readily dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 266° (decomp.). It was analysed after drying in vacuo at 180°. (Found: C, 49.5; H, 7.25; N, 19.7. C₉H₁₁O₃N₃ requires C, 50.5; H, 7.3; N, 19.7 per cent). It is represented as

C-4 was purified as its picrate, which crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetone, m.p. 199° (decomp.). [Found: C, 42.2; H, 4.5; N, 19.3. C₁₅H₂₀O₆N₆ (i.e. picrate of C₈H₁₁N₂O₂) requires C, 42.7; H, 4.7; N, 19.6 per cent]. This substance has the same formula as C-1, except that in ring NH-CO is NH-CH₃ in this compound. The substance furnishes chloroplatinate, m.p. 210° (decomp.) whence its M.W. is found to agree with the structure proposed. The other products were not found to be analytically pure.

Benzoylation of Chaksine.—Chaksine chloride (5.0 g.), dissolved in water (50 c.c.), was benzoylated with benzoyl chloride (10 c.c.) and alkali. After standing overnight, the benzoyl derivative solidified and was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140°. Siddiqui *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) reported two benzoyl derivatives, m.p. 273° and m.p. 146-52°. Our substance, m.p. 140°, is a simple dibenzoylbenzoate of chaksine (one benzoyl at CH₂OH and the other at one of the N atoms in NH-CO-NH of chaksine; the third as the benzoate at the quaternary N atom).

Acetylation of Chaksine.—Chaksine sulphate (1.0 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and pyridine (3 drops) in a boiling water-bath for 2 hours. Excess of acetic anhydride was removed in *vacuo* at 80°. The residue was poured into water (100 c.c.) and allowed to stand for 2 days. The white sticky solid could be easily crystallised from dilute acetic acid, dilute alcohol or a mixture of benzene and ether, yield 0.25 g., m.p. 200°. [Found: C, 58.1; H, 7.1; N, 9.2; CH₃CO, 41.0. Calc. for C₁₅H₂₀O₅N₂ (triacetyl): C, 58.4; H, 6.5; N, 9.1; CH₃CO, 41.6 per cent]. The amino-ethanol chain has been detached during drastic acetylation. The triacetyl compound is represented as

Oxidation with Chromic Acid.—Chaksine sulphate (5.48 g.), suspended in water (50 c.c.), was heated under reflux and the mixture was oxidised with a small amount of CrO₃ (4 g. in 2N-H₂SO₄, 40 c.c.) during 4 hours. Carbon dioxide was freely evolved. The solution on standing overnight gave a white crystalline deposit, which was repeatedly crystallised from hot very dilute sulphuric acid, m.p. 310° (decomp.). [Found: C, 39.4; H, 5.5; N, 14.6; S, 5.6. (C₉H₁₅O₄N₂)₂SO₄ requires C, 39.0; H, 5.4; N, 15.1; S, 5.8 per cent]. The exact formulation of the compound has not been possible. It is probably a mixture although it looks quite homogeneous under the microscope.

Emde degradation, Hoffmann degradation, zinc dust distillation, selenium dehydrogenation, soda-lime distillation did not provide any recognisable products. Chaksine sulphate and potassium hydroxide at 300° afforded only ammonia and potassium cyanide as recognisable products. Oxidation with NaOBr furnished bromoform as the only characterisable product.